

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

**D6.1: Dissemination, communication, and exploitation
activities (1st version)**

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used.

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AIDA	Awareness, Interest, Desire, Action
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation
BFMULO	B=Background/Foreground Knowledge, M=Making, U=Using the result, L=Licensing, O=Other
D	Deliverable
DAIRO	Data, AI and Robotics
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
EC	European Commission
EIP-Agri	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EU	European Union
EUIPN	European Union Intellectual Property Network
EUIPO	European Union Intellectual Property Office
FTO	Freedom to Operate
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KIPs	Key Impact Pathways
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MAA	Multi Actor Approach
PPP	Public Private Partnership
R&I	Research and Innovation
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time-bound
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOs	Strategic Objectives
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

While digitalization and the Internet of Things (IoT) connect people from all over the globe, in real life, rural areas are still not used to maximum benefit and remain isolated, urging for an impactful digital transformation change. To this day, the lack of appropriate digital connectivity solutions for rural areas are directly linked, mainly, either to the absence of the necessary technological infrastructure (non-sustainable for vendors) and/or to high connectivity service prices, making digital connectivity unaffordable for rural populations (non-sustainable for end users). XGain aims to address the need for high-speed digital connectivity in rural areas in a sustainable, balanced, and inclusive manner. For this purpose, XGain will deploy 6 heterogeneous Living labs (use cases) in terms of **location, connectivity needs, local needs, edge and connectivity potential solutions, and operational business models**. XGain will also produce several key exploitable results (KERs) that will offer extensive positive impact including:

- Knowledge Facilitation Tool (web platform)
- Set of sub-sectoral Technological Solutions
- Innovative Business Models
- Scientific Knowledge
- E-Trainings

The XGain Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DEC) provides the guidelines for successfully sharing the impacts and benefits of the project towards economy, society, science, and technology and defining concrete actions for use/reuse by five determined target groups:

- Rural Communities and Citizens
- Industries and SMEs
- Scientific Community
- Decision Influencers
- European & International Public & Regulatory Authorities

The aim of this document is to present a clear and coherent dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy which will serve as a cornerstone for all the outreach activities envisaged to be carried out throughout the project. Particular attention is given to the XGain's multi-actor approach, considering all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from the diverse set of partners and stakeholders ensuring broad communication throughout the project's duration.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan provides the guidelines for effectively sharing information within the consortium and an extensive strategy for transferring project knowledge and results to the targeted stakeholders. This document is the first iteration of the DEC plan which will be updated to monitor the plan's implementation (M18, M36).

1. Introduction

1.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

The increase in availability and usage of digital tools in all sectors (i.e., health, education, transportation, farming, etc.) demanded by the Covid-19 pandemic highlighted and amplified the already known digital connectivity inequalities existing between rural and urban areas. Digital accessibility and connectivity for rural communities and businesses still present a development challenge to many rural and remote areas. To this day, the lack of appropriate digital connectivity solutions for rural areas are directly linked, mainly, either to absence of the necessary technological infrastructure (non-sustainable for vendors), and/or due to high connectivity service prices making digital connectivity unaffordable for rural populations (non-sustainable for end users).

As the rural and coastal citizens are among the most vulnerable populations, every community's resilience, competitiveness, and capacity need to be enhanced, to contribute to and benefit from the upcoming transitions in a fair manner. Reducing the digital gap between rural and urban areas is of outermost importance; equally distributed digital opportunities translate to equal socio-economic opportunities for citizens and businesses. However, identifying a common solution for equipping rural communities with increased access to services, opportunities, and adequate innovation ecosystems is a challenging task, mainly due to the diversity of challenges and needs of different locations.

The XGain project in line with the ambitions of EU's Green Deal, the Digital Age and an Economy that works for people, ensuring that **"No one left behind"**, aims to strengthen the capacities of farmers, foresters, and rural communities through digital connectivity gains. XGain fosters a sustainable, balanced, and inclusive approach for rural and coastal areas by facilitating access to relevant stakeholders, to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity and edge computing solutions, and of related assessment methods.

The XGain consortium consists of **17 partners** coming from **12 European countries**. Together all partners form a complete group uniting the necessary expertise, skills, interdisciplinary knowledge, and resources that constitutes a representative value chain of actors (5 Research Technology Organizations, 9 SMEs, 1 Governmental Organization, and 2 large industrial companies) capable of achieving the demanding project goals.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities (Version 1)			
Initial report presenting the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities.			
TASKS			
T6.1. Dissemination, Communication and Capacity Building	Target groups and key messages	Chapter 3.3-3.4	Describes the Multi actor approach, target groups and prioritization
	XGain visual identity	Chapter 4.1-4.2	Presents XGain's logo, a set of graphic elements and images, templates for presentations and publications
	XGain's public website	Chapter 4.3.1	Provides the description of the web site as one of the major communication and dissemination channels
	Submitting high quality papers quality impact, peer-reviewed journals and magazines	Chapter 4.4.1	Pinpoints the number of publications and the scientific partners
	Presenting and publishing results in prestigious conferences	Chapter 4.4.2	Refers to a number of published results/position papers etc. presented in conferences/symposiums etc.
	Organizing workshops, trainings, conference sessions and tutorials. Capacity Building	Chapter 4.6	Identifies the consortium partners responsible for organising Technical Workshops, Training Programmes and Webinars
	Link the dissemination and communication activities with related initiatives and ongoing projects	Chapter 4.5	Provides a primary mapping of XGain's ambition to link with relative EU programmes and initiatives
	Practice abstracts	Chapter 4.4.4	XGain will publish short summaries of High-Speed Connectivity solutions for end-user understanding and utilization

1.2 Document Scope

The present Deliverable 6.1 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Activities (1st version) is developed within the framework of Task 6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Capacity Building; WP6 – Impact

Maximization and Outreach. The aim of the deliverable is to integrate the overall strategy of XGain, from day one, to define the goals of DEC activities, to identify the most efficient means to achieve them, and decompose them into a detailed implementation plan. To this end, the DEC plan sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited in order to effectively spread XGain activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences. Additionally, XGain DEC also aims to set the pace and a number of foreseen activities in order to place the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of XGain solutions.

This document (D6.1) acts as a reference point to all XGain's partners when carrying out DEC activities related to the project. Delivered in M06, D6.1 will be updated at M18 (version 2) and M36 (version 3), presenting progress on reaching Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as described within.

1.3 Document Structure

The document is outlined in 7 chapters, structured to appropriately present the overall XGain DEC objectives, strategy, target audiences, tools and means, channels and material for an efficient and effective implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation activities within the project lifespan.

This document is comprised of the following 7 chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project, the document scope and its overall structure.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the XGain project, including its objectives, methodology and scientific phases.

Chapter 3 describes the DEC Methodology including timeliness, the Multi Actor approach and target groups.

Chapter 4 specifies all dissemination and communication activities, tools, communication material and channel mix for XGain promotion.

Chapter 5 includes KPIs, reporting tools and their evaluation.

Chapter 6 presents the expected commercial and non-commercial results, means for their valorisation as well as their IP protection.

Chapter 7 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

References

Annex I provides the Deliverable Template

Annex II provides the logo variations and the colour palette that will be used for different media.

Annex III presents a table with XGain's partners' social media links.

Annex IV is the tool created for the identification of new KERs and their IP protection.

2 XGain Overview

2.1 XGain Objectives and Ambitions

XGain aims to address the need for high-speed digital connectivity and strengthen the capacities of farmers, foresters and rural communities in a sustainable, balanced and inclusive manner. For this purpose, XGain has primarily identified the Strategic Objectives that need to be examined as well as their methodological approach.

Going a step further from the current state of the art, the **core ambition** of XGain is to develop a cost-effective and environmentally friendly ecosystem of technologies, to assess the socio economic and environmental effects related to them and develop innovative business models in accordance with the performed assessments, integrated in a web based, user-friendly digital platform (Knowledge Facilitation Tool) intended for non-experts, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Graph of XGain's Knowledge Facilitation Tool (Figure taken from GA)

2.2 Strategic Objectives

To achieve the overall project's objective, the following **five (5) interdisciplinary Strategic Objectives (SOs)** have been defined, which are SMART, i.e., Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Time-bound. SOs correspond to real challenges stemming on real needs in real-time for all relevant rural areas' stakeholders. Figure 2 summarises the project's Strategic Objectives, their stemming challenges and XGain's contribution.

|
XGain Contribution |
|---|--|--|
| Identify end users' needs (public and multi-actor) for digital connectivity solutions, to co-create XGain system and use case requirements, designed in a sustainable, social accepted and fair manner. | Different rural areas (e.g. coastal, farms etc.) have different digital connectivity needs based on technology and cost-effectiveness. Furthermore, technological solutions should align with different social and environmental rural citizens' beliefs, routines and limitations. | XGain will offer tailor solutions to practitioners' and citizens' needs via a multi-actor implementation approach. |
| Design and deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool for non-experts, to support rural area citizens in their decision-making process on digital connectivity options with appropriate operational business models. | Various rural areas sectors (e.g. Farming, Health etc.) need appropriate services based on existing (or not) technological infrastructure, economic, environmental and social aspects, at different systemic levels such as farm, community or regional. | XGain will offer a decision-making support tool able to offer cost-effective solutions, in an environmentally friendly and social accepted manner for rural area citizens and stakeholders. |
| Develop, establish and facilitate the selection of the most appropriate innovative business models that will include systemic level and cross-sectoral approaches. | To create Innovative business models in 7 sectors such as: Aquaculture, Farming, Health etc. by integrating local techno-economic and socio-environmental studies as inputs in the Knowledge Facilitation tool and validate and fine-tune them in real-life case studies. | XGain will offer Innovative business models at systemic level and cross-sectoral, taking into account aspects of regional and/or systemic resilience and energy efficiency including the contribution to climate mitigation. |
| Validate the outcome of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool in 6 unique fields with different technical, environmental, societal and economical structures and needs. | Parallel to innovative business models, dry run tests as well as 6 use cases across Europe with different technological connectivity set ups will be used and accessed. Strong involvement of citizen associations as well as local authorities will be targeted in order to assess the social acceptance of the recommended solutions, including technological, environmental and business model aspects. | XGain will offer a fine-tuned Knowledge Facilitation Tool co-designed with rural areas' citizens and stakeholders based on real-life needs. |
| Accelerate the adoption of XGain solutions by the wider community and ensure impact maximization to the realization of sustainable, balanced and inclusive development of rural areas' vision. | A solid DEC plan should be used in order to inform and create traction for the facilitation of technology transfer and a new area in digital connectivity for rural areas. | Project results are to be made feasible to rural communities, farmers and foresters associations, and policy-makers. |

Figure 2: XGain's strategic objectives, challenges and contributions

2.3 XGain Methodology

XGain will utilize interdisciplinary expertise to effectively bring together a range of diverse actors to activate social, cognitive and scientific dynamics to develop a comprehensive solution for rural areas' digital connectivity inequalities. Thus, XGain's methodological approach will design, develop, analyse, combine and use the following interdisciplinary elements:

- Mapping of current digital connectivity technologies state of play and identification of existing requirements and challenges on a spectrum of sectors (livestock, farming, health etc.) at farm, community and regional levels.
- Social exclusion analyses (e.g. income, education, race, etc.) and social innovation analyses including scale (number of people and networks involved), scope (institutional and policy settings) and resonance (e.g. change of current habits) will be deployed to support co-creation among multi actors for each use case.
- Techno-economic analyses based on topology and access technological solution(s) will compare several digital connectivity alternatives and scenarios and suggest the most attractive by using economic indicators.
- Environmental Indicators and ICT analytics will be used to assess the Environmental and climate impact of the proposed interventions.

2.4 XGain’s Phases

XGain follows an iterative multi-step development approach in which user requirements and corresponding solutions evolve through multiple iterative collaboration rounds between all stakeholders taking into consideration the outcomes of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (XGain Tool). The core of the methodology is agile approach, adaptive development and continuous improvement based on iterative rounds including the following **4 phases** as shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: XGain’s Scientific phases

3 DEC Methodology and approach

A strong DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and will provide a concrete roadmap for partners in order to boost the growth of the XGain ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximize impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level. XGain sets clear Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination measures to promote the visibility of the project hence more benefits.

3.1 DEC Objectives and Time Plan

Communication Objectives

XGain's communication strategy is built upon the **Promotion Mix** and combines a wide but also targeted mechanism for communication actions. XGain will strategically carry out communication activities through electronic and non-electronic means. Through a funnelled approach, XGain will create and convey clear tailored and diverse key messages, raise awareness of project activities, enable active engagement, provide efficient dissemination and overall, maximize impact among key stakeholders and target groups at a broader social, policy, and industry level.

XGain's communication strategy has been designed and will be executed, with main focus on informing, promoting and passing all the project's activities to a spectrum of audiences such as citizens, media, investors and relevant stakeholders. Programmed to take place from the start of the project, XGain's communication strategy is directed towards:

- Engage and encourage positive reception and acceptance by end users, their advisors, and policymakers;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools, and channels;
- Market demand generation;
- Raise awareness on how public money is spent;
- Show the success of European collaboration;

Dissemination Objectives

XGain's dissemination strategy is based on two pillars, the **AIDA model** (Awareness, Interest, Desire, Action) and on EU's pillar for Open Science. The AIDA model follows a Multi-Actor (see Section 3.3), Multi-step and Multi-channel approach. It ensures that the project's advancements are widely spread to the intended targeted audiences with appropriate tools and that the key stakeholders are engaged early and actively participate during each of the project's phases. Dissemination activities are expected to diffuse the knowledge generated in the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact.

Open Science is designed and will be executed with a *modus operandi* towards democratization and free access to scientific knowledge and results generated by the project, for scientists and the general public to use-free of charge. At any time and as soon as XGain generates results, scientific (peer review) and other publications, data, etc. will be available to all interested stakeholders.

XGain applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the dissemination objectives as described below:

- Maximise results' impact
- Facilitate other researchers to advance their research
- Contribute to the advancement of the State of the Art

- Make scientific results a common good

Exploitation Objectives

Exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, XGain’s exploitation activities are recognized as the key enabler for the success of the project. All consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project’s results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring XGain results to all targeted stakeholders. A combination of activities will span throughout the project duration and will vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project’s lifetime. The objectives of the project’s exploitation measures include:

- Secure positive engagement from relevant stakeholders since it is important to attain both their contributions to the process as well as their willingness to use the results.
- Enhance and facilitate the exploitation of the project’s results both by the consortium partners and the stakeholders.

XGain intends to capture the added value of project results, which will be valorised by:

- Creating feasible paths to deliver project’s results to stakeholders interested in their use/reuse.
- Elaborating upon and defining new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to expedite development and commercialization when possible.

Time Plan

The DEC strategy is divided into four phases that span from M1 of the project and extend 3 years beyond the project’s completion, as shown in Figure 4. Each phase has an overarching objective that will provide focus to activities and create a steady workflow attuned to the work done and results produced by other WPs.

Figure 4: XGain’s DEC phases

3.2 DEC Methodology

The XGain DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC model** which includes the following key elements: Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Actions and Control through concrete KPIs, as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: SOSTAC model

3.3 Multi-Actor Approach

To help tackle the overall aim of the project, XGain will apply a Multi-Actor Approach (MAA). With a bottom-up approach, XGain will consider all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to achieve the project aims and ensure broad communication from the start. It will also extend to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the end-user;
- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience-appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry, society and government;
- Capitalising on partners' existing connections, networks and events programs;
- Including knowledge exchange activities and discussion in event programs;

Figure 6 presents the five different stakeholders' groups that are involved in XGain.

Figure 6: XGain’s stakeholder’s groups

Interactive innovation process

The ‘multi-actor’ approach is key for interactive innovation. The way diverse actors work well together (the ‘multi-actor approach’) is crucial for interactive innovation to deliver unique project results and benefits.

Multi-actor innovation brings together a diverse range of public and private innovation actors as shown in Figure 6, with complementary types and sources of knowledge to appraise, gather, co-create and disseminate practical solutions to real needs.

XGain’s multi-actor approach requires a participatory ‘bottom-up approach’, facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. Taking a ‘bottom-up’ approach to development allows members to be involved in the entire developmental process, from decision-making to evaluation. Interactive innovation is a social process rather than a ‘top-down’ scientific approach. Multi-actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, with the aim to plan and co-design practical and implementable solutions to real-life problems.

Figure 7: Key scenarios in multi-actor approach

The process of interactive innovation followed by XGain will involve the characteristic scenarios, shown in Figure 7³. Ranging from engaging and incentivizing actors/stakeholders to become involved, to co-creation, and applying new knowledge on the ground.

For each of the above-mentioned 6 key scenarios, relevant tools have been identified while some of them have already been tested during the proposal stage:

Scenario 1: ENGAGING

Tool: STAKEHOLDERS PRIORITISATION

The tool is used for the prioritization of the identified stakeholders’ groups assessing the types of actors involved in the multi-actor approach. The prioritization has already been made by the project partners during the proposal and team-building phase and it was based on the specific needs that XGain aims to address. An assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each of the stakeholders’ groups was also made. The specific order of this prioritization process is presented in Figure 8. Based on the outcomes and validation of D2.1 (Key Stakeholders mapping and functional requirements elicitation and analysis) M14, necessary adjustments will take place for the prioritization of the stakeholder groups if needed.

Figure 8: Prioritisation of stakeholders

Scenario 2: EXAMINING

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

Deliverable D2.1 (Key Stakeholders mapping and functional requirements elicitation and analysis) at M14 developed under WP2 (Interactive Definition of user-oriented requirements) will be dedicated to understanding the experiences, knowledge and perspectives of the stakeholders in the decision-making processes. This Multi-Actor Approach and deliverable D2.1 intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder’s experiences match

³ Better Rural Innovation: Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks. 2020. <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences. The journey mapping tool⁴ can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 3: CREATING

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

D2.2 (Social Innovation Analysis to ensure fair transition) at M16 from WP2 will be used in order to identify and promote social inclusiveness for all related actors. For that purpose, social exclusion analyses will map out all relevant factors resulting in exclusion of stakeholders and citizens, and the relative urgencies of each factor for each stakeholder, by means of in-depth interviews and questionnaire surveys targeting citizens. This step will contribute to 'fair transitions' in several manners, referring to a design of innovations that not only consider the technological innovations, but also the associated change to behaviours, rules, regulations and governance, what it is referred to as 'informational governance'.

VARI (Value Analysis of Relative Importance) will be used to assess relevant urgencies for inclusiveness among rural citizens according to a set of relevant indicators (covering income, education, race, and age factors) and will contribute to the co-design of potential ways to overcome the urgencies to enhance innovative and smarter solutions to increase access to services, opportunities and adequate innovation ecosystems.

Scenario 4: ADDRESSING

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation. TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 5: APPLYING

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and How?

The tool has been used during the project development stage allowing partners to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks.

Scenario 6: EVALUATING

Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool is used for facilitating partners to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans. The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

⁴ Ginka Toegel & Jean-Louis Barsoux, 2015, based on 'Act, Think, Speak, Feel'. <https://hbr.org/2016/06/how-to-preempt-team-conflict>

3.4 Target Groups and Key Messages

Target groups have been identified to categorically define all parties that could have an interest in the project and its results. To summarise the benefit to each group, key messages have been created (Figure 9) and the general breakdown of activities and channels meant to engage each group has been defined (Table 2). Table 2 will become updated accordingly, if needed, on the second version of the DEC Plan (D6.3) at M18, based on the project’s results.

Figure 9: XGain’s Target Groups and Key messages

Table 2: Dissemination and Communication activities and channels

DC ACTIVITIES/ CHANNELS	TARGET GROUPS				
	DECISION INFLUENCERS	PUBLIC REGULATORY AUTHORITIES	SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY	INDUSTRIES & SMES	RURAL COMMUNITY & CITIZENS
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS	✓	✓	✓		
TECHNICAL PUBLICATIONS		✓		✓	✓
SOURCE CODE REPOSITORY			✓	✓	
Q&A PLATFORM		✓		✓	
WORKSHOPS & TRAININGS		✓	✓	✓	✓

JOINT ACTIVITIES WITH RELEVANT INITIATIVES	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
STANDARDS & POLICY CONTRIBUTION	✓	✓			
PROJECT WEBSITE & SOCIAL MEDIA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
E-NEWSLETTER & EMAIL CAMPAIGNS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
GENERAL SPREADING	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
POLICY FORA & HUBS	✓	✓			
BLOGS			✓	✓	✓
PRINTED MATERIAL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MULTIMEDIA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

4 Communication and Dissemination Channels, Tools and Activities

4.1 Visual Brand Identity

XGain’s branding design involves a holistic approach towards the establishment of a long-lasting, easily recognizable visual identity. XGain’s visual identity aims at the recognition, perception and identification from relevant stakeholders of the project’s core values, key messages and offered services. It includes colours, letter fonts, logos, presentations, word templates and guidelines. It constitutes the basis on which all consortium partners, throughout the 3 years of operation of the project, will prepare their communication material, to promote the XGain project on all channels in a coherent way.

All digital products that are foreseen to be derived, online media presence and offline materials will be made coherent in order to create brand awareness among the targeted audience. The visual identity guidelines are in line with the obligations of beneficiaries regarding information and communication and dissemination measures included in Article 17.2 — Visibility — European flag and funding statement and 17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer of the Grant Agreement Nr. 101060294.

4.1.1. Logo

The logo is the main tool to create direct visual recognition of the XGain project, therefore, was chosen to be simple, give a hint of a story but above all to be easily recognisable. The XGain logo includes the name of the project as its main concept using a clear and modern font and an icon representing digital airwaves (like the wifi icon) and is optimised for both web and print. The logo will also be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness, throughout the project’s lifetime and beyond.

Several colour variations have been selected for different uses. Colours are optimised for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is high enough for black and white printing. Logo variations, fonts and colours (Brand Book) are presented in Annex II. The most frequently used logo for most of the communication and dissemination material is shown in Figure 10 below:

Figure 10: XGain’s Logo

4.1.2. Templates

XGain will be presented in numerous events, conferences, and meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results. A presentation template (ppt) as well as a word (doc) template have been designed in line with XGain graphic identity in order to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition (Figure 11).

Figure 11: XGain's presentations and Word template

XGain's deliverable template (Figure 12) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title) as well as the writer's information. For the full version of the deliverable template see Annex I.

Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains

Dx.y: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner)]

DX.Y: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101060294		
Project Acronym	XGain		
Project Title	Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains		
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-03		
Project Start Date	September 1 st , 2022	Project End Date	August 31 st , 2025
Project URL	xgain-project.eu		
Work Package	WPx WP Title		
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)		
Deliverable type ¹ Dissemination level ²	XXX XXX		
Contractual due date	DD Month 20YY	Actual submission date	DD Month 20YY
Lead Author (s)	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]		
Contributors	[Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)]		
Internal reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]		

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¹ R: Document, report; DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan design; DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc; DIMP: Data management plan; ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.
² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables tagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified P-U/EU-P = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2022/644; Classified C-U/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2022/644; Classified P-U/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2022/644

© XGain Page | 1

Figure 12: XGain's deliverable template

4.1.3. EU Emblem

All XGain dissemination and communication material will acknowledge the requirements set out by the European Union and include the EU flag and the source of funding.

Figure 13: EU Emblem

4.1.4. Disclaimer for Publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

4.2 Communication Material

XGain communication material has been designed and produced aimed to promote and simultaneously increase stakeholder and public awareness of the project. For multiplying the sphere of influence, both digital and physical forms have been created.

Offline communication products have the added advantage of being physical, tangible and will occupy space to captivate audiences during the project's participation in events and conferences. XGain's roll-up banners will be used to promote the project *per se* as well as to present the results arising from the use cases (Living labs) (Figure 14) while XGain's brochure with information regarding the project, partners, lack of digital connectivity in rural areas as an issue, living labs as real-time demonstrations for possible solutions, the knowledge facilitation tool and the overall added value can be seen in Figure 14.

These materials focus on a more visually engaging way of raising awareness about the project, its aims, activities and results. It is advantageous to follow certain rules when utilising offline material – regardless of the implementation strategies; well-prepared headlines, wisely colours usage, focus on benefits – and keep the tone and the message aligned to the intended target audience. To achieve this goal, all of the aforementioned will be in line with XGain's brand book (ANNEX II), to ensure that the produced communication material aligns with the project's visual identity.

Figure 14: XGain's Roll-up Banner and Brochure

4.3 XGain Channel Mix

4.3.1. Website

XGain’s website (<https://xgain-project.eu>) has already been developed and the landing page of the website was released on M2 (Figure 15). The project’s website is the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and XGain’s stakeholders to access project development and results, and to grasp and assess the added-value and the impact of digital connectivity solutions in rural areas. The site will be regularly updated with contributions from all partners. It will host all the public dissemination deliverables, promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, workshops and demos events, press releases, printed material, publications etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. It will also host digital visualisations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. Finally, the website will also be mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximising the impact of the project.

Figure 15: XGain’s website

XGain’s website has a twofold role as it will serve as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project’s aims, providing new updates, documents for download and enabling access to social media accounts of XGain and, furthermore, it will act as a resource centre for research on topics related to digital connectivity technologies, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in **M6**, the XGain website is hosted at www.xgain-project.eu and contains the following sections and features.

- **Home/Landing page**
 - Includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube), a button for sign-up in the XGain’s newsletter, XGain’s Objectives and expected results, all partners’ logos, EU’s Emblem and a navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project.
- **About**
 - Concept and Methodology

- Objectives
- Consortium
- Use Cases in Living Labs
- **Dissemination and Communication**
 - Public Deliverables
 - Workshops & Demos
 - Publications
 - Brochures & Flyers
 - Newsletters
- **News and Events**
 - Press releases and posts will be the main content and will inform stakeholders of all project's activities and upcoming events.
- **Contact**
 - All contact information for the XGain project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders through email (info@xgain-project.eu).
 - Contact form for messages.
- **Privacy Policy**, together with **Cookies Policy** have also been included in the XGain website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

In order to ensure the proper visibility of the website and monitor the relevant KPIs, the platform "Google Analytics" has been used, which is a well-established web analytics tool provided by Google and tracks website's traffic, as seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Website Metrics

4.3.2. Social Media

XGain aims to have a strong social media presence and establish bidirectional communication channels, to better reach out and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, four media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

1. The most cost-effective set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups;
2. The most adequate, valid and powerful media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders; and

- The most popular social media platforms used by XGain's partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

XGain is registered and active (M2) on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube. In order to monitor the social media accounts and ensure their effectiveness, the respective KPIs have been tracked (Figure 17), in line with KPIs targets claimed in the Grant Agreement. The analytics tools of the aforementioned platforms have been used to collect the relevant data.

Figure 17: XGain's social media metrics

To maximise visibility and impact of the project's events and outcomes, XGain will exploit the consortium's already-developed social media networks. Consortium's partners are expected to share, publish and retweet content from the XGain social media accounts and XGain website, thus, increase traction for project-related work and increase traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels. An Excel file was created (Annex III) to gather all the needed information from each partner such as the links to their official social media accounts.

After channel selection, there are several parameters to consider for distributing consortium's social media content:

- Interactivity is the main pillar of the generated content and is the optimum method to reach and engage an audience. Posts will be easily understood by non-specialists to facilitate interaction.
- Eye-catching posts will lead to higher conversions with prioritisation into visuals and graphics will make the piece unique.
- Adaptability of the social media assets to the format and functionality of the several devices. The asset will be used in such a frame to maximise their placement, especially taking into consideration the placement on mobile devices.

Creating hashtags relevant to the project and its outcomes will help reach target audiences and make it easy to find XGain generated knowledge. Hashtags divide the project main topics into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and will help increase visibility in the social media environment, while they will make XGain's messages stand out and influence relevant communities. Further tracking of the hashtags will facilitate the consortium to analyse quantitative and qualitative data. The project has set official distinctive hashtags such as **#XGain**, **#connectivity**, **#edgecomputing**, **#5G**, **#drones**, **#HorizonEurope** and others which are used to monitor the posts related to the project (Figure 18).

Figure 18: XGain’s hashtags

Additionally, to effectively share information on social media our consortium will need to design posts based on how the audience consumes the message. Figure 19 explains the steps that a visually appropriate social media post should contain and based on these high efficiency posts will be created during the project’s lifespan:

Figure 19: Content of the XGain's social media posts

4.3.2.1. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/xgain-project/>) was created to network with XGain target audiences and promote the project's activities. As such, all project's news will be published on LinkedIn profile and partners will have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes and attract a wider audience. Figure 20 provides an overview of XGain's LinkedIn profile.

Figure 20: XGain's LinkedIn page

4.3.2.2. Facebook

XGain's Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/xgain.project/>) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level.

Figure 21: XGain's Facebook page

4.3.2.3. Twitter

A Twitter account was created (https://twitter.com/XGain_project) to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policymakers and advisors. XGain will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact and post news, events and updates on the project's status.

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format makes it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter will also be used to connect to "high influencers" in the research and business topics of the XGain project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 22: XGain’s Twitter profile

4.3.2.4. YouTube

YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnVXXUozJfcdfkNnziyiPIQ>) will be used in order to host and promote XGain’s videos, which will be of wide variety, such as interviews, case studies, demos etc.

Figure 23: XGain's YouTube channel

4.3.3. E-Newsletter and Email Campaigns

An electronic newsletter will be published every 4 months (starting M04) to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This will include the latest developments, use case results

and activities as well as upcoming events, workshops, demonstrations and where to find recent reports and publications.

Figure 24: 1st XGAIN Newsletter

Subscription can take place at events as well as in XGain’s website. Upon Newsletter registration, XGain will pay special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the users’ personal data. Newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All

relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European and international legal framework, and the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the XGain Newsletters and all collected data will be stored and saved in the responsible partner’s servers. Users’ data will be inaccessible to third-parties. More detailed description on data collection, storage and handling will be presented in the respective deliverables (D6.12 Data Management Plan M6-^{1st} Version, M18-^{2nd} Versions, M36-^{3rd} Version). Professional marketing platforms (i.e. Sendinblue and Mailchimp) will be used to automate the distribution among contact points. Furthermore, to achieve broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, XGain partners will be encouraged to promote newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

Let's keep in touch!
Stay up to date with our latest news and more!
Sign up to our newsletter now!

First Name

Last Name

Email Address

Submit

Figure 25: XGain's Newsletter registration bar/tab

The first issue of the newsletter was produced in December 2022 (M04), with content provided by partners and was sent to all consortium partners for review after its completion. Partners will provide their feedback and then ICCS (XGain’s coordinator) will proceed in its web publication and promote it to all social media accounts of the project. All newsletters will also be uploaded and remain available on the project’s website. Newsletters will be published every 4 months (3 per year) and anticipate 2.000 newsletter subscribers over the course of the project.

The 36 months planning for the newsletter is as follows:

- 2022 – December-Issue No1 ([Published](#))
- 2023 – April-Issue No2
- 2023 – August-Issue No3
- 2023 – December-Issue No4
- 2024 – April-Issue No5
- 2024 – August-Issue No6
- 2024 – December-Issue No7
- 2025 – April-Issue No8
- 2025 – August-Issue No9

The proposed structure of each newsletter is:

- Introduction
- Project Update / Key news, deliverables and project events
- News & Events
- Resources for further reading (suggested by all partners)

4.3.4. Blogs

XGain will connect and execute periodic broad promotion activities in open communities, blogs, non-profit organisations and channels such as: Gitter Communities, Nature.com and DownToEarth.

4.3.5. Multimedia

XGain will produce multimedia material (a short video for each use case) to have a self-explanatory and appealing presentation of the project, leveraging available distribution channels of promotion (e.g., YouTube, Vimeo). Also, a set of video interviews, both from scientific partners and end-users, to collect inputs, taking advantage of plenary meetings and events of relevance will be implemented.

4.3.6. Press Releases

Press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities and developments to a broader audience as well as addressing more specific stakeholders. To maximise influence on local stakeholders, the consortium will translate all press releases into all consortium partners' languages (Figure 26). More specifically, the first press release was developed after XGain's kick-off meeting which took place at M2 and was distributed to various digital media (Figure 27).

Figure 26: Translation of Press Releases

The screenshot shows the website ypaithros.gr with a navigation bar containing categories like 'Ευφυής Γεωργία', 'Πληρωμές', 'Περιβάλλον', 'Σύγχρονος Αγρότης', 'ypaithrosTV', 'εισορές & τεχνολογία', 'τόπος', 'αγορά', 'χρηματοδοτικά εργαλεία', 'παραγωγική αλυσίδα', and 'ευρώπη & κόσμος'. The main article is titled 'Η ΠΚΜ εταίρος στο έργο Xgain για τη γεφύρωση του ψηφιακού χάσματος ανάμεσα σε αστικές και αγροτικές περιοχές'. Below the title is a group photo of people. To the right, there is a 'ΔΗΜΟΦΙΛΗ' section with several news items, including 'Η νέα ΚΑΠ με απλά λόγια: Όλες οι δράσεις στήριξης των αιγοπροβατοτρόφων' and 'Διαβάστε στην «ΥΧ»: Πληρωμές στα τυφλά'.

Figure 27: First Press Release published at ypaithros.gr

4.3.7. Demo events

CAPT, I2CAT, ART, BENCO, JS and EVILVO are XGain’s consortium technological provider partners responsible for the use cases (Living Labs) and will be leading the spreading and the citizen engagement in the demo countries (Greece, Spain, Lithuania, Croatia, UK, and Belgium respectively).

4.3.8. Policy Fora and Debate Hubs

XGain will promote and encourage Science-Policy dialogue regarding digital connectivity in rural areas. XGain will contribute to discussions and make recommendations on how the developed solutions could enhance the sustainable, balanced and inclusive development of rural areas.

4.3.9. Exploitation & Communication Tools

XGain will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project’s results, shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Exploitation & Communication Tools

4.4 Publications

XGain foresees developing several scientific, industry, standards and policy publications, practice abstracts as well as source code to influence a wide range of targeted stakeholders and to promote the project and its findings. All publications will implement Open Access and Open peer-review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science. Thus, all publications will be published in Open Research Europe and/or open access journals. A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

- Far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
- Greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community;
- Improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse XGain's results thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

4.4.1. Scientific Publications

XGain will strive to publish at least 10 peer-reviewed scientific papers (including Abstracts in scientific conferences) in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing scientific

credibility for the project's work. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research partners (ICCS, WR, EVILVO, I2CAT, ZSI) and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the XGain project.

4.4.2. Technical Publications

Besides the creation of Press Releases and scientific publications, XGain will publish 25 related publications to high quality technical blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogues, books or any other reference from technology providers (bottom-up), as well as references related to the application scenarios domains under consideration (top-down), to make the project and its results known to industrial stakeholders.

4.4.3. Standards and Policy Publications

To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, XGain aims at influencing standards and policy-making, thus obtaining the seal of approval for the newly implemented components and consequently pushing them into production environments, presenting project's results for defining future R&I directions based on project's acquired knowledge. Standards and Policy contributions by XGain will enable the uptake and positive impact of digital connectivity solutions in rural areas, while engaging policymakers from the targeted policy areas.

4.4.4. Practice Abstracts

XGain will produce **5** practice abstracts, in the form of summaries for practitioners, in the EIP Agri format dedicated to the activities and outcomes of the **6** Living Labs that take place in **6** countries over **6** biogeographical regions. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/practice regarding the deployment of High-speed Digital Connectivity solutions via XGain's Knowledge Facilitation Tool that can be used by the end-users in order to enhance the sustainability performance and competitiveness of rural areas.

4.4.5. Source Code Publication

XGain will make accessible its software repositories through well-known distributed source code platforms. Well-established repositories are **GitHub** and **Bitbucket**.

4.4.6. Q&A Platform

Conversations about the project repository would be concentrated in reference sites. The selected Q&A platform will be the **Stack Overflow**, the largest, most trusted online community for developers to learn and share knowledge.

4.5 Joint Activities with relevant Initiatives

To further amplify and maximise the impact and outreach of the project's results and to feed them into related international work streams, joint dissemination activities will be contacted. XGain consortium has already strong cooperation with ongoing relevant partnerships, networks and initiatives, including DAIRO through **eBOS**, AIOTI through **EVILVO**, 5G-PPP through **CAFA**, EIT Digital through **CAP** and Copernicus through **ICCS**. XGain has already started bilateral communication discussions for common Dissemination event organization and/or participation with the co-financed by the same Horizon Europe call COMNECT (<https://www.horizoneurope-commect.eu>).

4.6 Workshops and Trainings

During the project duration, **ICCS**, **CAFA** and **I2CAT** will organise the technical workshops (virtual and physical), **INC**, **EVILVO**, and **BENCO** will undertake the training sessions (online and physical training tutorials) and **WR**, **RAIN** and **ZSI**, will organise webinars, as a means of knowledge transfer, wider outreach and sustainability.

4.7 Event Planning

Event planning will take part in two phases. On a 6-month basis an event planning form will be sent to partners to describe their future events attendance (Figure 29). A brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for XGain (i.e. workshop, booth presence, conference participation etc.) will support the decision-making process. This form has been sent to partners, and the responses will be compiled using an online reporting tool for easy reference and record keeping.

1. XGain Event Planning						
#	Type of event	Event link (if applicable)	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential XGain involvement
	<i>e.g., Conference, Seminar, Webinar, Workshop, Exhibition, etc.</i>		<i>DD/MM/YY / City, Country</i>	<i>e.g., Local, Regional, National, European, International level</i>	<i>The target groups that will attend the event (e.g., Private Sector, Agri-rural Communities, Academia & Researchers, Associations, General Public)</i>	<i>e.g., Presentation, Booth, Workshop, Banner ect.</i>

Figure 29: XGain's event participation template

The second phase involves the selection of events. This will be done based on the guidelines below in Figure 30. These necessary actions and time of occurrence will ensure event participation alignment with the project's objectives and budget. These will need to be adapted to individual activities, since numerous factors can result in varying steps and deadlines.

Figure 30: XGain's guidelines for event selection and planning

5 Monitoring and Evaluation

5.1 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are concrete, measurable targets used for monitoring and evaluating the project’s progress and enabling adaptation when necessary. A set of dissemination and communication KPIs and targets have been identified and presented below in Figures 31 and 32.

Dissemination KPIs

Figure 31: Dissemination KPIs and targets

Communication KPIs

Figure 32: Communications KPIs and targets

KPIs have been distributed between two reporting periods (M1-M18, M19-M36) in which the DEC plan will be updated in 3 versions.

DISSEMINATION KPIs (TARGETS)		REPORTING PHASES	
		M1-M18	M19-M36
D.1	SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS		
	Peer-reviewed papers (including conference papers) (10)	0	10
	Technical publications (e.g. articles, blog posts) (25)	10	15
D.2	ORGANIZATION & PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS		
	Participation in conferences (10)	4	6
	Booths in industrial fairs and exhibitions (10)	4	6
D.3	SOURCE CODE REPOSITORY		
	Publicly Available Deliverables (28)	15	13
	Source Code Repository Publications (2)	0	2
D.4	Q&A PLATFORM		
	Participation in Scientific Conversations (25)	10	15
D.5	WORKSHOPS & TRAININGS		
	Technical Workshops (10)	0	10
	Online Training Tutorials (8)	0	8
	Webinars (12)	0	12
D.6	JOINT ACTIVITIES WITH RELEVANT INITIATIVES		
	Participation in Symposiums/Fairs (9)	4	5
	Banners in each event (3) (total 27)	13	14
	Brochures to be distributed (300)	150	150
D.7	STANDARDS & POLICY CONTRIBUTION		
	Standards Contributions to different Organisations (5)	0	5
	Policy Recommendations (5)	0	5

Figure 33: Dissemination KPIs per reporting period

COMMUNICATION KPIs (TARGETS)		REPORTING PHASES	
		M1-M18	M19-M36
C.1	PROJECT WEBSITE		
	Unique visitors from M12 (1500)	3000	1200
	Unique visitors from M36 (5500)		
C.2	SOCIAL MEDIA		
	Size of online community (5000)	2200	2800
	Monthly average of online impressions (500)		
C.3	E-NEWSLETTERS & EMAIL CAMPAIGNS		
	E-Newsletters (9)	4	5
	Mailing List Contact Points (2000)	2000	0
C.4	GENERAL SPREADING		
	Press releases (15)	7	8
	Organised events (6)	6	0
	People per event (100)		
C.5	POLICY FORA & DEBATE HUBS		
	Fora & Hubs to interact (7)	2	5
	Contributions to Policy Fora/Debate Hubs (15)	7	8
C.6	BLOGS		
	Unique publications to Blogs (25)	10	15
	Different Blogs (10)	4	6
C.7	PRINTED MATERIAL		
	Hard copies (brochures, flyers, etc.) (2500)	1000	1500
	Roll-up Banners (8)	2	6
C.8	MULTIMEDIA		
	Short videos & Interviews (7)	1	6
	Views (1000)		

Figure 34: Communications KPIs per reporting period

Moreover, to effectively share the responsibility for spreading project results and maximising the impact derived from partners’ expertise, experience and networks, KPIs and targets have been assigned to each partner, as shown in Tables 3 and 4. The reporting mechanism (described in Section 5.2) will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets. The first reporting period of the project is fundamental for establishing connections and building interest around the project and will be used to:

- Map stakeholders and their needs that must be addressed;
- Develop the project’s website, visual identity, communication materials and social media channels;
- Establish and implement the protocol for deciding events, publications and identifying synergies;
- Begin outreach to other projects, initiatives;
- Participate in events and publish press-releases and newsletters;
- Familiarise partners with all communications channels, templates, and protocols

Table 3: Dissemination KPIs per partner

#		Target	ICCS	BENCO	CAFA	CAPT	EBOS	EVILVO	I2CAT	INC	ICOM	RAIN	RDFCM	WR	ART	ZSI	TID	ASTRO	JS
		WPG PMs	4	4	3	4	6	10	10	4	3	28	6	2	4	3	3	4	2
		Budget [other costs]	19450	8750	25000	9200	1534	7000	18000	0	1500	28400	0	10000	8750	13000	0		
Dissemination KPIs																			
D.1	Scientific Publications																		
D.1.1	Peer-reviewed papers (including conference papers)	10	2					2	3					2		1			
D.1.2	Technical publications (e.g. articles, blog posts)	25	5					4	6					5		5			
D.2	Organization & participation in events																		
D.2.1	Participation in conferences	10	3	1	1	1			2						1	1			
D.2.2	Booths in industrial fairs and exhibitions	10	1	1	2	1			2		1				1	1			
D.3	Source Code Repository																		
D.3.1	Publicly Available Deliverables	28	5			1	4	3	1	2	1	7		3		1			
D.3.2	Source Code Repository Publications	2					2												
D.4	Q&A Platform																		
D.4.1	Participation in Scientific Conversations	25	5	2	2	2		3	4		1				2		2	2	
D.5	Workshops & Trainings																		
D.5.1	Technical Workshops	10	4		3				3										
D.5.2	Online Training Tutorials	8		2						1									
D.5.3	Webinars	12						5				7		2		3			
D.6	Joint Activities with relevant Initiatives																		
D.6.1	Participation in Symposiums/Fairs	9	1		1	1	1	1	1			2				1			
D.6.2	Banners in each event	3 (total 27)	3		3	3	3	3	3			6				3			
D.6.3	Brocures to be distributed	300	30		30	30	30	30	30			90				30			
D.7	Standards & Policy Contribution																		
D.7.1	Standards Contributions to different Organisations	5						3	2										
D.7.2	Policy Recommendations	5						1	1					1		1	1		

Table 4: Communication KPIs per partner

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	ICCS	BENCO	CAFA	CAPT	EBOS	EVILVO	I2CAT	INC	ICOM	RAIN	RDFCM	WR	ART	ZSI	TID	ASTRO	JS
		Target	ICCS	BENCO	CAFA	CAPT	EBOS	EVILVO	I2CAT	INC	ICOM	RAIN	RDFCM	WR	ART	ZSI	TID	ASTRO	JS
		WPG PMs	4	4	3	4	6	10	10	4	3	28	6	2	4	3	3	4	2
Dissemination KPIs																			
C.1	Project Website						Leader												
C.1.1	Unique visitors from M12	1500					1500												
C.1.2	Unique visitors from M36	5500					5500												
C.2	Social Media											Leader							
C.2.1	Size of online community	5000										5000							
C.2.2	Monthly average of online impressions	500										500							
C.3	e-Newsletters & Email Campaigns		Leader																
C.3.1	e-Newsletters	9	9																
C.3.2	Mailing List Contact Points	2000	2000																
C.4	General Spreading			Leader		Leader		Leader	Leader						Leader				Leader
C.4.1	Press releases	15										15							
C.4.2	Organised events	6		1		1		1	1						1				1
C.4.3	People per event	100		100		100		100	100						100				100
C.5	Policy Fora & Debate Hubs							Leader											
C.5.1	No. of Fora & Hubs	7						2	2			1		1		1			
C.5.2	Contributions to Policy Fora/Debate Hubs	15	2	1		1		4	1	1		2		1	1	1	1		
C.6	Blogs								Leader										
C.6.1	Unique publications to Blogs	25	1	2	2	2	1	2	3	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	
C.6.2	No. of different Blogs	10		1		1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1		1			
C.7	Printed Material											Leader							
C.7.1	No. of hard coppies (brochures, flyers etc)	2500		350		400		300	750						350				350
C.7.2	Roll-up Banners	8		1		1		1	1			2			1				1
C.8	Multimedia			LL leader	LL leader	LL leader		LL leader	LL leader			Leader			LL leader				
C.8.1	No. of short videos & interviews	7		1	1	1		1	1			1			1				
C.8.2	No. of views	10000		1500	1500	1500		1500	1500			1500			1500				

5.2 Reporting Tools

Event and communication reporting

Partners will be asked to report on their dissemination and communications activities on a monthly basis. Feedback will be collected from partners using an online Google Form consisting of two key categories: i) Events and Activities and ii) Other Communication Activities, as seen in Figure 35. In this way, partners are able to provide a detailed report with their monthly Dissemination and Communication Activities, including all the relevant information, such as the place, date and type of an event that have participated or organised, links of any promotional digital material, photos etc.

The image shows a screenshot of a Google Form. At the top, there is a header banner with the XGain logo, which consists of the letters 'XGain' in a bold, sans-serif font. The 'X' is green, and 'Gain' is black. To the right of the text is a blue graphic of a Wi-Fi signal. Below the banner, the form has a white background with a light blue border. The title of the form is 'XGain- Communication & Dissemination Activity Report'. Below the title, the text reads: 'Dear XGain partners,' followed by a paragraph: 'This form will be used for reporting all activities and events organized or attended by the XGain consortium members as well as communication channels engaged by the consortium members on a monthly basis.' Another paragraph follows: 'You are kindly requested to fill in the relevant information by the last day of the month so we may update the website and social media in a timely manner. Information will also be used to track KPIs and ensure we are meeting our targets.' The form concludes with 'Sincerely,' and 'Rainno Team'.

Figure 35: Google Form for collecting partner information regarding events and communication

6 Joint Exploitation and IPR Strategy

XGain’s exploitation plan contains concrete actions to be implemented both during and after the end of the project. These actions have been designed to build upon project’s results and to be expanded as the project progresses. Through XGain’s Key Impact Pathways (KIPs), the main aim of the exploitation plan is to ensure the optimal use of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) for both **commercial** and **non-commercial** use and therefore, to speed up their uptake by targeted stakeholders, ensuring wide use and maximum impact to the economy, society, science and technology.

For this purpose, XGain will develop a dedicated Innovation report and IPR management strategy (D6.8) at M8 (version 1) which will be updated at M36 (version 2, D6.9) as well as a Market Analysis, exploitation and sustainability strategy (D6.7) at M22, for ensuring the protection of results generated by XGain and the overall sustainability of XGain respectively.

Table 5: XGain’s Commercial and non-commercial KERs at a glance (taken from GA)

	OPEN ACCESS	MONETISED
Knowledge facilitation tool	Open as Community Edition	Post Project
A set of technological solutions	Not Applicable	Post Project
Business models	During the Project	Post Project
Scientific knowledge	During and Post Project	Not Applicable
E-trainings	During the Project	Post Project

6.1 Exploitation Methodology

A specific procedure has been set for the definition of the project’s KERs, the identification of new KERs other than those already identified, their validation, characterisation and development of the final exploitation plan of each KER from a specific partner, group of partners or external organisation.

The **first step** involves the development of the “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool, which validates the existing knowledge and information about the project’s Key Exploitable Results and possible IPRs that the partners have already identified.

In this tool, the list of the identified KERs is provided where partners are asked to state the scope of exploitation, the KERs’ target groups, the means of exploitation and to identify possible IPRs that derive from the exploitation of the identified project’s results. For each partner there is a separate sheet with their organisation’s acronym providing them with an individual space for information and updates.

The tool has been already shared with the partners and is available for further update at any time (Annex IV).

The **second step** involves the identification of possible additional exploitable results that may be developed during the project. Towards this direction, constant communication with partners, updates for their progress on the 6 use cases either through the regular partners’ meetings or through direct communication with the involved partners, help in identifying possible exploitable results, commercial or non-commercial.

To this end, certain procedures and steps have been designed and presented in Figure 36 below:

INCLUSION OF NEWLY IDENTIFIED KERs

Figure 36: Mapping of possible KERs procedure

When one or more partners identify a new KER, the partner has to inform the Coordinator providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. The partner has to provide all relevant information about this KER in their individual sheet in the “KERs Inventory & IPRs” online tool, covering at least the following aspects:

- Scope of exploitation
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation (how)
- Link to possible IPRs

The **third step** refers to the assessment of the exploitation strategy for each KER. To efficiently determine involvement of project partners in each of the KERs the BFMULO Matrix will be implemented, in which the partners will state their exploitable intentions using the following list:

B = IPR’s on background information, information, excluding foreground information, brought to the project from existing knowledge, owned or controlled by project partners in the same or related fields of the work carried out in the research project.

F = IPR’s on foreground information, Information including all kinds of exploitable results generated by the project partners or 3rd parties working for them in the implementation of the research project. To have an F in an exploitable result it is necessary that a partner has a task(s) in the project related to that very result.

M = Making the products, manufacturing and selling or directly implementing it through own facilities and skills.

U = Using the result, implemented with own knowledge to develop new ranges of products or newer processing. Furthermore, the direct or indirect utilisation of foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.

L = Licensing the result, therefore earning from a negotiation towards third parties outside the Consortium.

O = Other, any other exploitation means (e.g.: consultancy, provide services, etc.).

Table 6: BFMULO Matrix

#	KER1	KER2	KER3	KER4	KER5
ICCS					
BENCO					
CAFA					

CAPT					
EBOS					
EVILVO					
I2CAT					
INC					
ICOM					
RAIN					
RDFCM					
WR					
ART					
ZSI					

The **fourth step**, which will be applied in later stages, when the project’s results will be more concrete, a characterisation table will be provided to partners which will exploit the project’s key results. Each result requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type, whether it can be commercialised, and if Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are required and who will exploit the result. The characterization table will be offered to partners to characterise exploitable results (Table 7).

Table 7: Characterization table for potentially exploitable results

CHARACTERISATION OF EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	
MARKET 	Who will the customer be and what benefits will they receive?
	What is the anticipated time to market?
	What is the size of the market in M€ and relevant trends?
	What is the approximate price range of this result and price of licences?
	Who are the competitors?
	How will this result rank against competing products/services in terms of price and/or performance?
STEPS TOWARDS	When is the expected date of achievement?

EXPLOITATION 	What are the foreseen barriers to successful implementation?
	What are the costs incurred after the project and before exploitation?
	Which partners will be involved in results development?
IPR STATUS 	Have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When?

This table aims also to collect information for the market analysis and business models that will be developed by the end of the project. The information and feedback included in the characterization table will serve as the foundation of the final exploitation plan of the KERs.

6.2 Exploitation pathways

A distinct exploitation plan will be established for each result, however, broad pathways may be defined for commercial results and others for non-commercial results. Examples are included below.

6.2.1 Commercial Results

For commercial results the business model canvas and a market analysis will be used.

Business model canvas

The business model canvas (Figure 37) offers a single page visualisation of the path to commercialisation and defines several key components including:

- **Key partners** who will be responsible for the creation and exploitation of the result
- **Key activities** required by the value proposition
- **Key resources** needed including human, physical, intellectual, financial
- **Value proposition** describing
 - The value of the result
 - The problem that is being addressed
 - The specifics of the product/service being offered
 - Which customer needs are being met?
- **Customer relationships** expected to be established, delivered, and maintained with end users, which ones already exist and at what associated costs
- **Distribution channels** that work best, are preferred by customers and are cost-efficient
- **Customer segments** the results are targeting, who are the most important customers
- **Cost structure**, including the most important costs, the most expensive resource, and activities and whether the outcome is cost-driven or value-driven

- **Revenue streams**, what values customers are willing to pay, what do they currently pay, what are the possible streams (e.g., product, subscription fee, usage fee)

Figure 37: Business Model Canvas for commercial results

6.2.2 Non-commercial Results

For results that will not be exploited for financial gains, different approaches will be required but could include:

Modified Business Model Canvas

The single page visual offered by the business model canvas (Figure 38) is a tool that can be modified to plan alternative exploitation pathways for certain results and suitable specific alterations will be made, such as:

Customers have been changed to users and revenue streams have been replaced with:

- Sustainability (how the result can be maintained beyond the duration of the project).

NON-COMMERCIAL RESULT – MODIFIED BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Figure 38: Modified Business Model Canvas for non-commercial results

Sustainability plan

A sustainability plan will be created for the long-term exploitation of non-commercial results to ensure their use/reuse continues after the project is no longer funded by Horizon EU and will consider:

- Responsible partners
- Resources required (including person hours, technology)
- The value of results and what needs to remain exploitable
- Specific tasks/ activities required for the result to remain valuable
- Partnerships or joint actions that could better support long term exploitation than only the partners themselves
- Alternative funding sources

6.3 Key Exploitation Results (KERs) and Unique Proposition Value (UVP)

XGain has predefined and selected five Key Exploitable Results, available for use/reuse by partners and target group stakeholders. Figure 39 describes each result, who is responsible for it and who it will benefit.

Figure 39: XGain's Key Exploitable Results

6.3.1 XGain's Market Analysis, Exploitation & Sustainability Strategy

Based on commercial KERs (Figure 39) as well as additional results that may be developed during the lifespan of the project and have monetisation perspective, XGain will compile at M22 a Market Analysis, Exploitation & Sustainability plan (D6.7) based upon techno-economic, socio-economic and sustainability indicators to incentivise, acquire and retain profitable customers and subsequent commercial growth.

Market analysis

Market analysis will strategically identify the attractiveness, dynamics and market potential of XGain's results. Result specific analyses will expand the business model canvas and build upon the market analyses, through a qualitative and quantitative assessment, conducted by WP6 aim to:

- **Determine/confirm the target market** to be reached and gather related information such as the size of the market both in terms of volume and in value, the associated customer segments and buying patterns;
- **Determine the Global competition as well as the competitive landscape** with similar products/services that try to provide digital connectivity solutions in rural areas as well as their strengths and shortcomings;
- **Recognise the economic environment** in terms of barriers to entry and regulatory imperatives;
- **Leverage XGain's results** to promote new customer value propositions;

Sustainability Analysis

XGain's sustainability analysis will provide the **roadmap for achieving long-term goals and will document strategies to continue the program, activities, and partnerships** by answering key questions such as:

- Future Income streams and mitigation strategies concerning them;
- Financial Projections;
- Marketing strategy for ensuring XGain's sustainability;
- Ways to attract new customers and businesses;
- Possible future diversification to fit with changing technologies and the future needs of end-users;

6.4 IPR Strategy

The XGain consortium aims to develop a comprehensive and feasible strategy for the IP generated throughout the lifespan of the project. XGain's IPR strategy aims to align the impact pathways of the project with its outcomes and impacts thus, enhancing its overall credibility and making it "fit for purpose". XGain's IP approach will give due thought to balance between open science publication results and plans to adequately protect IP for commercial exploitation.

All KERs are potentially subject to IPR management. Innovation Report and IPR management D6.8 and D6.9 will be created by M8 and M36 respectively coupled with D6.7 Market analysis and exploitation and sustainability plan by M22, will provide a detailed plan for each result and outline concrete IPR measures to be taken by the partners. XGain will examine the protection of any result that could potentially be commercially or industrially exploited, and if possible, reasonable, and justified, protect them.

XGain will produce significant research results and technological innovations. Hence, a strategy that will handle all IP rights matters will be developed, creating an encouraging environment for further exploitation of the generated discoveries and knowledge. As such, XGain handles IPR Management on a three-level approach covering the whole lifecycle of the project:

IPR at proposal phase: XGain's consortium has already proceeded with a Preliminary Identification of results under IP regime and has identified outputs that can be subject to IP/ownership, such as the Knowledge Facilitation Tool. Furthermore, it has concluded preliminary searches in various databases (Google patents, Patents lens, EUIPO, EUIPN, WIPO) and revealed that there are no trademarks on XGain's acronym, logo or the full title of the project. A first Freedom to Operate (FTO) analysis has been done and no blocking point has been found.

During the project: *a. IPR at Grant Preparation Phase:* A preliminary assessment of intangible assets through the Horizon IP Scan service will be utilised, aiming to identify any IP issues that the consortium’s SMEs will potentially encounter. *b. IPRs Stemming from Use Cases:* XGain will give emphasis to the protection of IPRs derived from the use cases, ensuring that any IPR generated shall rest with the industry (farming, forestry, etc.) that created it and can further exploit it commercially. Under this framework, a set of both protective and supportive measures (such as the obligation to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements) will be undertaken by the consortium to create confidence in involved participants, with attention to the IBMs that will be developed under the use cases and be tested during the demonstrations, ensuring a transparent allocation of IPRs and a fair exploitation by the beneficiaries. *c. Democratisation of Scientific Knowledge:* The consortium will publish the overall project results through publications, seminars and in the project website, without charging intellectual property rights. Further, partners will deposit scientific peer-reviewed publications in a centralised repository (Open Research Europe) as mandated by the HE “Open science policy”.

Post-Project IPR Strategy: Since the FTO analysis resulted in no barriers, the pre-identified and newly generated IPRs can and will be protected. Given that XGain is based on community-led innovations, the knowledge facilitation tool will remain open as a **community edition** and research partners of the consortium will sustain it. A commercial edition of the tool, enriched with new integrated cross-sectoral data, could also be developed post-project.

Identification of new IPRs- project procedure

As the project progresses additional IPRs might be identified by the partners. To this end, a certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in the Figure 40 below:

Figure 40: Newly identified IPRs procedure

The identification of new IPRs is closely related to the identification process of KERs described above. In that way, when a new IPR is identified, the partner follows the same procedure by informing the Coordinator on the relative IPR that is linked to the KER as presented in Annex IV.

Following, the partners are asked to validate the new IPR. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new IPR is validated, it is included in the project’s IPR list.

7 Conclusion

D6.1 “First Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities”, has provided an overview of the communication, dissemination and exploitation phases during the whole project lifetime. The intention of this document is to outline the initial DEC plan which will be implemented during the first period of the XGain project, as well as the tools that will be utilised in order to reach DEC’s KPIs and project’s audience.

More specifically, the document covers a wide range of key activities (as well as sets their timelines) to be conducted to meet the dissemination, communication and exploitation targets. All partners will be actively involved in the communication and dissemination of XGain aiming to assure the proper exploitation of the project’s outcomes and maximise the impact.

The Second Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities (D6.3), due M18, will be an updated version of the DEC plan. It will evaluate the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions beyond M18 until the third iteration (M36). The second version will focus on the diffusion of the scientific and technological information generated under the umbrella of the 6 User Cases/Living Labs and emphasis will be placed on sparking interest in the User Cases and broadening stakeholder engagement with the project activities and results.

Annex I: XGain's Deliverable template

Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains

Dx.y: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner)]

Funded by the European Union

DX.X: Deliverable Title			
Grant Agreement No.	101060294		
Project Acronym	XGain		
Project Title	Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains		
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-03		
Project Start Date	September 1 st , 2022	Project End Date	August 31 st , 2025
Project URL	xgain-project.eu		
Work Package	WPx WP Title		
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)		
Deliverable type ¹ Dissemination level ²	XXX XXX		
Contractual due date	DD Month 20YY	Actual submission date	DD Month 20YY
Lead Author (s)	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]		
Contributors	[Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)]		
Internal reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]		

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¹R: Document, report; DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc; DMP: Data management plan; ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

²PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)	Name
V0.1	DD/MM/YYYY	10	Initial Deliverable Structure	Contributor(s) (organization)	Name
V0.3	DD/MM/YYYY	30	xxxxxxx	Contributor(s) (organization)	Name

DX.X: Deliverable Title

XGain Consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Name	Short name	Country
1	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	ICCS	EL
2	BENCO BALTIC DOO ZA SAVJETOVANJE IUSLUGE	BENCO	HR
3	CAFA TECH OU	CAFA	EE
4	IKE KAPTEN KOOUTS	CAPT	EL
5	EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED	eBOS	CY
6	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW - EN VISSERJONDERZOEK	EVILVO	BE
7	FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL A CATALUNYA	I2CAT	ES
8	INCITES CONSULTING SA	INC	LU
9	INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS	ICOM	EL
10	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RAIN	EL
11	REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT FUND OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	RDFCM	EL
12	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
13	UAB ART21	ART	LT
14	ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH	ZSI	AT
15	TELEFONICA INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO SA	TID	ES
16	Astrocast SA	ASTRO	CH
17	JONATHAN MICHAEL SMITH	JS	UK

DX.X: Deliverable Title

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DX.X: Deliverable Title

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description

DX.X: Deliverable Title

1 Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary³ for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

³ [text]

DX.X: Deliverable Title

2 Introduction

Goal of this section is to provide a brief outline of the objectives of the specific XGain Deliverable, how are those aligned and relevant with the overall project, and what was the approach followed in order to achieve them.

2.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map XGain Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

Dx.y Title

Respective extract from formal Deliverable Description

TASKS			
Task Number & Title	Respective extract from formal Task/Subtask Description	Respective Chapters or Sections numbers within this document addressing GA described Task/Subtask	Briefly outline how addressed the respective document section(s) cover the described GA Task activities

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this section, a description of the Deliverable's Structure should be provided, outlining the respective Chapters and their content.

2.2.1 Example Heading 3

Paragraph 1 Text text text

Paragraph 2 Text text text

DX.X: Deliverable Title

3 Example Heading 1

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

3.1 Example Heading 2

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

3.1.1 Example Heading 3

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

- List example
- List example

3.1.1.1 Example Heading 4

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

Table 2: Example caption for tables

Title	Title

Text colour pallet [Black, text 1]

#336788 [R51, G103, B136]
#2D9C76 [R45, G156, B58]
#005F83 [R0, G95, B131]
#595959 [R89, G89, B89]

Tables colour pallet

#336788 [R51, G103, B136]
#F2F2F2 [R242, G242, B242]
#2D9C76 [R45, G156, B58]

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Figure 1: Example caption for figures

DX.X: Deliverable Title

4 Conclusions

Purpose of this section is to summarize the outputs of the specific deliverable and how it has contributed to the overall project goals. Where applicable, do identify business impact, map business benefits with XGain innovative offerings and record user evidence.

Here, you may also pinpoint identified best practices, elaborate on potential future improvements, and specify the evolutionary roadmap forward.

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Example of landscape layout (including custom header and footer)

Paragraph Text text text

Paragraph Text text text

“Note: When using this layout, make sure that the section breaks remain in the correct place. Use CONTROL +* to switch paragraph marks and make sure there is a "section break" at the end of this page and as the last element on the previous page.

Also make sure that the footers of sections following a page in landscape format are copied from the previous section, if necessary.”

Annex II: XGain’s Brand Book

XGain
xgain-project.eu

Funded by the
European Union

Colors

 C:0 M:0 Y:0 K:100		
 R:0 G:0 B:0 #000000		
 PANTONE 447 C		

Typeface

HelveticaNeueLT Std Med Bold

Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee
Ff	Gg	Hh	Ii	Jj
Kk	Ll	Mm	Nn	Oo
Pp	Qq	Rr	Ss	Tt
Uu	Vv	Ww	Xx	Yy
		Zz		

Variations

Annex III: XGain's Partners Template with Social Media Links

#	Affiliation	Twitter	Facebook	LinkedIn	YouTube
1	ICCS	I-SENSE GROUP/ ICCS	ISenseGroup	ISenseGroup/ICCS	N/A
2	BENCO	N/A	N/A	Benco baltic d.o.o.	N/A
3	CAFA	CAFA Tech	CAFA Tech	CAFA Tech	N/A
4	CAPT	N/A	N/A	CAPTAIN Coach	N/A
5	EBOS	N/A	eBOS Technologies Ltd	eBOS	eBOS
6	EVILVO	ILVO	Instituut voor Landbouw-, Visserij- en Voedingsonderzoek	Instituut voor Landbouw-, Visserij- en Voedingsonderzoek	N/A
7	i2CAT	i2CAT	N/A	i2CAT Foundation	Fundació i2CAT
8	INC	inCITES Consulting	N/A	inCITES Consulting	N/A
9	ICOM	INTRACOM TELECOM	Intracom Telecom	Intracom Telecom	Intracom Telecom
10	RAIN	Rainno The Innovation Rainmakers	Rainno - The Innovation Rainmakers	Rainno The Innovation Rainmakers	N/A
11	RDFCM	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
12	WR	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
13	ART	N/A	Art21: Agro ir maisto inovacijos	ART21	N/A
14	ZSI	ZSI Research Policy	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation - ZSI	N/A	N/A
15	TID	Telefónica Research	N/A	N/A	N/A
16	ASTRO	Astrocast	N/A	Astrocast	N/A
17	JS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Annex IV: Identification of new KERs & IPR process

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation			Target groups (to whom)	Means of exploitation	Linked IPRs to the KERs		
Please validate the already identified KERs (1-5) and add any other exploitable results if relevant		Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)			Please validate (see note for the list of target groups)	Please indicate the means of exploitation, where relevant	Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant		
		If "other", please identify		Other			If "other", please identify		Other
1	Knowledge Facilitation Tool	Commercial			Farmers, Foresters and their associations, Municipalities, citizens of remote areas	This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.			
2	Set of Technological Solutions	Commercial			Technology providers, software developers, broadband and mobile network providers, ICT SMEs	This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.			
3	Business Models	Commercial			Potential Investors in rural Domain, service and technology providers, local Authorities of rural communities and isolated areas	This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.			
4	Scientific Knowledge	Scientific	Policy-making		Academic and Research Institutions, individual and young researchers, Policy and decision-makers at EU, national, regional and local levels	This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.			
5	e-Trainings	Commercial	Training and education		Rural, Coastal and Urban communities, focusing on women, youth and indigenous people	This was initially identified as an exploitable result for your organisation. Could you please clarify how you envision its exploitation.			
6	Other individual or joint exploitable result (if any)								
7	Other individual or joint exploitable result (if any)								

Identified Background

Please validate the background described in the Consortium Agreement or revise accordingly

This is the description in the Consortium Agreement for your organisation: "No data, know-how or information of the partner is needed by another Party for implementation of the Project or Exploitation of that other Party's Results"